

THE DIFFERENCES BETWEEN USING TEXT-BASED AND ART-BASED METHODS TO DEVELOP STUDENTS' SELF STUDY SKILLS

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Abstract:

The conditions of living, formation, training, and teaching have changed in the modern digital age. Everything has been changing lately, thus studying attitudes must also change. In a contemporary comprehensive school, the curriculum is still uniform; it is based on objective standards that have been historically updated. Many contemporary teachers lament the absence of an effective strategy that prioritizes the uniqueness of each student. The education received in school does not provide the student with a clearly defined, positive motivation to select a career, interests, or path in life. In the twenty-first century, international education has a rising role.

Key words: training, formation, teaching innovative methods, technology, video, audio, interactive methods, objective standards, studying attitudes.

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Introduction

The majority of people consider a "text" to be a written work, such as a brief article, an email, or even a poem. But keep in mind that a text could also be an audio text, such as a song, a speech, or a dialogue. Either solution will work, however keep in mind that the grader may choose the one that makes the most sense. For instance, the passive voice is rarely employed in casual conversation but is used rather often in news reports and newspaper articles

Therefore, if it is unsure to determine what kind of material to utilize, think about the grade level that you want to teach. What circumstances or contexts do you typically see it in. then choose your text accordingly. You will probably have access to the text if you are utilizing a course book. Make sure the wording is concise and incredibly straightforward. You won't want to spend much time on the text itself if your class lasts between 45 and 90 minutes; you'll want to get to the grammar as soon as you can. This may sound apparent, but keep in mind that the main objective of an agricultural lecture is to teach the grain. That implies that you don't want to have to spend any time studying new vocabulary or other sophisticated grammar that isn't your target language.

So, aside from the target language examples you plan to include in the text, make sure the vocabulary and sentence structures you use are nice and easy if you're composing the text yourself. If you're using a text from a course book or anywhere

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else, give it a critical review. Is it more than 200 words long, roughly. Consider this your official permission to take action if the answer to either of those questions is yes. At least a few different examples of the target language should be included in the text. Ideally, it will also provide examples in the negative and question forms, but this is not required. You just need more than one example so that, later in the course, you may use them to assist the pupils recognize patterns in meaning and form.

Artistic techniques can serve as a catalyst for audiences to delve into challenging subject matter that may be difficult to express through conventional means. Jennica and Maya have succeeded utilizing art-based methodologies to examine relational meaning. In other words, such techniques are valuable when: a) contextual exploration is crucial; b) establishing connections between unrelated concepts is necessary (such as how social determinants of health may impact a program); or c) delving into complex emotional experiences. Additionally, theories-based approaches allow for a range of knowledge acquisition, extending beyond the use of text and language to encompass spatial and temporal connections, as well as the ability to depict concepts in tangible ways. Artistic methods enable participants to connect ideas in innovative and spontaneous ways, pushing them beyond their comfort zones and encouraging novel forms of self-expression. Art-based data gathering approaches are inherently participatory, involving artists in the creation and interpretation of data. These inductive techniques are designed to describe and explore ideas, beginning with observations and working with participants to develop an understanding of the meanings and inferences that can be drawn from the art.

There are five methods for gathering data based on principles:

1. Literary (e.g. poetry)
2. Performative (e.g. interpretive dance, theatre)
3. Visual (e.g. pictures, collage)
4. Audiovisual (e.g. film, video)
5. Multimedia (e.g. graphic novel, art installation)

Chomsky asserts that the inventive quality of human language is a crucial characteristic. He contends that there must be an inherent aspect of human language that is innate, accessible to us because we are human, and defined in our genetic composition. Chomsky has demonstrated that the intellect cannot confine itself to rigid patterns of conduct [9,12].

LeVine stressed the significance of social exchange in intellectual growth. LeVine viewed interaction as the solution to conquering the instability of the symbols we personally create. LeVine connected the function of social exchange to the value of language. LeVine linked language's function in the advancement of conceptual and logical comprehensions, making it an essential element in his notions on intellectual growth. LeVine related the function of social exchange in intellectual growth to the role of language. As for LeVine, language is naturally a social factor, mainly due to the traditional nature of words, which is crucial for conceptual growth.

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